

The Redlich–Peterson isotherm for aqueous phase adsorption: Pitfalls in data analysis and interpretation

Khim Hoong Chu ^{a,*}, Mohd Ali Hashim ^a, Yannice Tatiane da Costa Santos ^{b,c}, Jean Debord ^d, Michel Harel ^{e,f,g}, Jean-Claude Bollinger ^h

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603, Malaysia

^b Environmental and Sanitary Engineering Course, Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology—Campus Juazeiro do Norte, Juazeiro do Norte 63048-080, Brazil

^c Department of Biological Chemistry, Regional University of Cariri, Crato 63105-010, Brazil

^d Service de Pharmacologie-Toxicologie, Hôpital Dupuytren, 87042 Limoges, France

^e Université de Limoges, Laboratoire Vie-Santé UR 24 134, Faculté de Médecine, 87025 Limoges, France

^f Institut de Mathématiques de Toulouse, UMR CNRS 5219, 31062 Toulouse, France

^g Université de Limoges, INSPÉ de l'Académie de Limoges, 87036 Limoges Cedex, France

^h Université de Limoges, Laboratoire E2Lim, Faculté des Sciences et Techniques, 87060 Limoges, France

* Corresponding author.

E-mail: khimchu@gmail.com (K.H. Chu)

Abstract

The Redlich–Peterson isotherm, a variant of the Sips isotherm, is widely used to describe the adsorption characteristics of water contaminants. Despite its popularity, this isotherm is susceptible to misuse and misinterpretation. In this article, we aim to bring to light the various deficiencies associated with the Redlich–Peterson equation, encompassing faulty mathematical formulations, unverified mechanistic interpretations, erroneous linearized versions, unnecessary parameter constraints, incorrect parameter units, inappropriate model comparisons, model misidentifications, and flawed thermodynamic calculations. These deficiencies often stem from a lack of mathematical expertise or a poor understanding of adsorption modeling, and occasionally, from egregious negligence. Our primary goal is to draw attention to these

pitfalls and encourage researchers to steer clear of them. By providing guidance and shedding light on these issues, we aim to foster the judicious application of the Redlich–Peterson equation in the analysis and interpretation of adsorption equilibrium data.

Keywords: Adsorption isotherm; Radke–Prausnitz; Misuse; Misapplication; Misinterpretation; Misconception.

1. Introduction

When is misuse not misuse?

When everybody does it.

– Trudgill (1998)

In 1948, Sips introduced a three-parameter isotherm equation to describe gas adsorption on a heterogeneous catalyst surface (Sips, 1948). The Sips equation emerged as a viable alternative to the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms for data correlation, garnering substantial attention within the gas adsorption community. In 1959, Redlich and Peterson modified the Sips equation, resulting in the creation of a novel isotherm termed the Redlich–Peterson (R–P) equation (Redlich and Peterson, 1959). Although the R–P equation was highly effective in correlating gas adsorption data, its adoption was limited during the 1960s, being applied in only a handful of studies (Peterson and Redlich, 1962; Meyer and Weber, 1967; Lee and Weber, 1969). The resurgence of the R–P equation occurred in the late 1970s, propelled by Jossens et al. (1978), who used it to describe the adsorption of various water contaminants on activated carbon.

Following the pioneering study by Jossens et al. (1978), numerous investigations have showcased the efficacy of the R–P equation in the realm of water contaminant adsorption. It has gained recognition as a high-performing isotherm model, proving especially valuable when the adsorption process deviates from a simple Langmuir model. However, our examination of existing literature has revealed numerous instances of the R–P equation being misapplied and misunderstood. In fact, a significant portion of previously published studies employing the R–P equation, even in reputable journals, is afflicted by some form of error. Recognizing the impracticality of addressing every flawed study, this research will focus on a specific subset of the voluminous literature, emphasizing recent studies featured in leading journals.

The goal of our research is to spotlight several common deficiencies associated with the R–P equation, providing guidance for researchers to steer clear of these pitfalls. These deficiencies often stem from inadequate mathematical proficiency, a limited understanding of adsorption modeling, or simply from carelessness. By identifying and rectifying these errors,

we seek to enhance the accuracy and reliability of research in this domain. Specifically, we aim to encourage researchers to pay closer attention to the capabilities and limitations of the R–P equation. In this context, our contribution aligns with the efforts of other research groups striving to caution the adsorption community about the risks associated with the improper use of mathematical models (Schwaab et al., 2017; Tran et al., 2017; Xiao et al., 2018; Inglezakis et al., 2019; Mudhoo and Pittman, 2023).

2. Isotherm equations

2.1. The Sips equation

Sips (1948) derived an energy distribution function for gas adsorption on a heterogeneous catalyst surface by using the empirical isotherm presented in Eq. (1). In this equation, p denotes the equilibrium gas pressure, q is the corresponding solid phase concentration, and A , B , and N are fitting parameters. At high pressures, where $Bp^N \gg 1$, Eq. (1) simplifies to $q = A/B$, and the Langmuir model also simplifies to this form. At low pressures, where $Bp^N \ll 1$, Eq. (1) approximates the Freundlich equation and can be expressed as Ap^N . While commonly known as the Sips equation, Eq. (1) is occasionally referred to as the Langmuir–Freundlich or Freundlich–Langmuir equation.

$$q = \frac{Ap^N}{1 + Bp^N} \quad (1)$$

2.2. The R–P equation

Redlich and Peterson (1959) demonstrated that the low- and high-pressure limits of the Sips equation could be interchanged by setting the exponent N in the numerator of the ratio in Eq. (1) to 1, as outlined in Eq. (2), where a , b , and n serve as fitting parameters. When p is high, Eq. (2) transforms into the Freundlich equation with $q = (a/b)p^{1-n}$. At low pressures, Eq. (2) approximates Henry’s law, expressed as $q = ap$, and the Langmuir model simplifies to this form as well. Referred to as the Redlich–Peterson equation, Eq. (2) could just as well be called the inverted Sips equation. Fig. 1 provides a summary of the characteristics of the Sips and R–P equations under low- and high-pressure conditions.

$$q = \frac{ap}{1 + bp^n} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Characteristics of the Sips and R-P equations under low- and high-pressure conditions.

It is plausible that Redlich and Peterson published their equation in the *Journal of Physical Chemistry* as a playful tribute to Sips, whose work had been featured in a journal with the title's words inverted — the *Journal of Chemical Physics*. The remarkable recognition and citations garnered by Redlich and Peterson's paper are noteworthy, considering its brevity — spanning merely half a printed page and featuring only a slight modification to the Sips equation.

In a subsequent publication (Peterson and Redlich, 1962), Redlich and Peterson conceded that Eq. (2) represented a purely empirical isotherm model. To impart theoretical significance to their equation, they endeavored to integrate parameters like the saturation value of q and vapor pressure into Eq. (2). Despite their efforts, the modified equation failed to attract significant attention. It is worth noting in passing that Otto Redlich (1896–1978) is most renowned for the Redlich–Kwong equation of state and for contributing several papers on the thermodynamics of electrolyte solutions (Reif-Acherman, 2008).

In the context of liquid phase adsorption, Eqs. (1) and (2) are expressed as Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively, with c representing the equilibrium liquid phase concentration and q denoting the corresponding solid phase concentration. Notably, a significant correlation was identified between the parameters a and b when using Eq. (4) to model type I or favorable equilibrium data (Joshi et al., 2006). Through the re-parameterization of Eq. (4), this correlation between the parameters was successfully reduced.

$$q = \frac{Ac^N}{1 + Bc^N} \quad (3)$$

$$q = \frac{ac}{1 + bc^n} \quad (4)$$

2.3. Comparing Sips and R-P

Considering the R-P equation as a variant of the Sips equation, significant differences in their data-fitting capabilities are unlikely. To verify this assertion, Fig. 2 illustrates the fits of both equations to a previously reported experimental isotherm, depicting the adsorption of acid red 18 dye on activated carbon (Vargas et al., 2012). This isotherm exhibited a steep ascending segment at low concentrations and a distinct plateau at high concentrations, often termed a rectangular isotherm. Both equations provided satisfactory fits to the dye isotherm, with a slightly superior fit observed for the R-P equation ($R^2 = 0.985$) compared to the Sips fit ($R^2 = 0.970$). To further evaluate the adequacy of the R-P and Sips equations, a visual inspection of the residual plots may be conducted. Despite the R-P equation lacking a finite saturation limit (reducing to the Freundlich equation at sufficiently high concentrations), Fig. 2 demonstrates its surprisingly effective fit to the dye data characterized by an apparent plateau.

Fig. 2. Fitting acid red 18 adsorption data (Vargas et al., 2012) with the Sips equation [Eq. (3)] and the R-P equation [Eq. (4)].

The Sips equation is capable of fitting type V or sigmoid isotherm data when the exponent N exceeds 1, enabling it to track both symmetric and asymmetric sigmoid isotherms (Brião et al., 2023). Fig. 3 illustrates a sigmoid isotherm from the work of Cheknane et al. (2021), depicting the adsorption of Cd(II) on activated carbon. Both the Sips and R-P equations were used here to fit the Cd(II) isotherm data. Fig. 3 indicates that the Sips equation accurately captured the sigmoid shape of the experimental isotherm ($R^2 = 0.986$), consistent with the findings in the original study (Cheknane et al., 2021). In contrast, the performance of the R-P equation was notably unsatisfactory ($R^2 = 0.953$), as its mathematical structure does not allow

for the description of sigmoid curve shapes — a limitation not foreseen by Redlich and Peterson when they modified the Sips equation.

Fig. 3. Fitting Cd(II) adsorption data (Cheknane et al., 2021) with the Sips equation [Eq. (3)] and the R–P equation [Eq. (4)].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mathematical forms

A key point of discussion revolves around the various mathematical formulations used to represent the R–P equation. Eq. (4) stands out as the predominant form of the R–P equation used in the literature. In the 1970s, Jossens et al. (1978) and Mathews and Weber (1977) were among the pioneers in using Eq. (4) to describe the adsorption of organic contaminants on activated carbons.

Various formulations of the R–P equation [Eq. (4)] can be derived through a superficial analogy to the Langmuir model. These versions commonly integrate a saturation capacity parameter. Eq. (5) serves as a representative example (Kinniburgh, 1986), where q_s denotes the saturation capacity parameter and k represents the equilibrium constant. A comparison between Eqs. (4) and (5) reveals that $q_s k = a$ and $k^n = b$. The advantage of this representation lies in the fact that k and the equilibrium constant in the Langmuir model share the same units. However, it is crucial to note that Eq. (5) introduces four distinct numerical parameters, namely q_s , k , k^n , and n . Consequently, k should not be equated to the Langmuir equilibrium constant. Recent studies employing Eq. (5) for data correlation include the works of Belkassa et al. (2021), Boubaker et al. (2021), Gómez-Avilés et al. (2022), Abdulkareem et al. (2023), and Madeira et al. (2023).

$$q = \frac{q_s kc}{1 + (kc)^n} \quad (5)$$

Eq. (6) introduces another version of the R–P equation that mirrors the mathematical form of the Langmuir model (Song and Shin, 2005). In this instance, $q_s k$ and k replace a and b in Eq. (4), respectively. However, the parameter k in Eq. (6) introduces a unit conflict issue. When c is expressed in mg L^{-1} , the numerator's k assumes the units of L mg^{-1} , while the denominator's k takes on the units of $\text{L}^n \text{mg}^{-n}$. Eq. (6) has also been extended to describe bisolute systems, as illustrated in Eqs. (7) and (8) (Repo et al., 2011). The presence of conflicting units in k , k_1 , and k_2 suggests that Eqs. (6)–(8) are based on erroneous assumptions. Therefore, they should not be used for interpreting experimental equilibrium data. Recent examples of data fitting using Eq. (6) include the studies by Chaparro et al. (2019), Khaledi et al. (2021), Mangwandi et al. (2022), Bedadeep et al. (2023), and Rouibah et al. (2023).

$$q = \frac{q_s kc}{1 + kc^n} \quad (6)$$

$$q_1 = \frac{q_{s,1} k_1 c_1}{1 + k_1 c_1^{n_1} + k_2 c_2^{n_2}} \quad (7)$$

$$q_2 = \frac{q_{s,2} k_2 c_2}{1 + k_1 c_1^{n_1} + k_2 c_2^{n_2}} \quad (8)$$

Eq. (9) introduces another expression of the R–P equation incorporating q_s . Ge et al. (2022) used Eq. (9) to describe the adsorption of cadmium and lead on hydrochar, mistakenly assuming it to represent the R–P equation. Eq. (9) denotes, of course, the Sips equation.

$$q = \frac{q_s kc^n}{1 + kc^n} \quad (9)$$

3.2. Mechanistic interpretations

Many researchers adhere to the belief that fitting a set of arbitrarily chosen isotherm models to equilibrium data offers a means to discern the adsorption mechanism of a contaminant-adsorbent system. The primary criterion used for evaluating the models is the goodness of fit, commonly assessed by the coefficient of determination R^2 . The theoretical validity of a model is considered supported if its R^2 score surpasses the competing R^2 values. For instance, if models A and B yield R^2 values of 0.95 and 0.94, respectively, the inference is drawn that the theoretical foundations of model A are correct, while those of model B are deemed incorrect. This oversimplified method of comparing models has given rise to various unfounded assertions about the R–P equation, some of which are outlined below.

Xu et al. (2022): “the Redlich–Peterson isotherm model,...was more suitable for describing the adsorption process of all heavy metal(loid)s ($R^2 > 0.95, \dots$), which indicated that the adsorption was not ideal monolayer adsorption, but a hybrid chemical reaction–adsorption process...”

Li et al. (2022): “The R^2 value of three isotherm models were in the order of Redlich-Peterson isotherm ($R^2 = 0.9483$) > Langmuir isotherm ($R^2 = 0.9351$) > Freundlich isotherm ($R^2 = 0.8767$). The adsorption of Cr(VI) on PPS could be better described by Redlich-Peterson isotherm model,...Therefore, the adsorption of Cr(VI) on PPS could be determined as a hybrid chemical reaction sorption process...”

Singh and Datta (2022): “The fitting parameters from the Redlich–Peterson isotherm suggest a larger amount of monolayer adsorption and lesser amount of multilayer adsorption of NH_4^+ on BNPP.”

Kumar et al. (2022): “The regression coefficients for Langmuir and Redlich-Peterson isotherms were comparable, which suggests that there could be involvement of specific heat of adsorption (mean energy of adsorption) as well as multilayer adsorption (not an ideal monolayer sorption event).”

The statements above suggest that the theoretical framework of the R–P equation is linked to a combination of chemical reaction-adsorption and multilayer adsorption processes. However, this raises the question of whether deriving valuable insights into the adsorption mechanism is achievable merely by fitting the R–P equation to experimental isotherms. Can the verification of the R–P equation’s theoretical assumptions rely solely on data fitting? An even more critical question pertains to the physical basis of the R–P equation. As previously mentioned, the R–P equation is an empirical model without a well-defined physical foundation. It serves as a variant of the Sips equation, itself an empirical model (where the Sips parameters may have statistical significance concerning energy distributions for heterogeneous adsorbents). Peterson and Redlich (1962) themselves admitted, “Equation 1 [our Eq. (2)] is a purely empirical relation and cannot furnish a basis for strict interpretation.” Neglecting the empirical nature of the R–P equation has led to mechanistic interpretations that are, at best, tenuous and, at worst, nonsensical.

3.3. Linearized versions

Before the widespread availability of computers, it was a common practice to transform nonlinear algebraic expressions into linear ones to analyze nonlinear relationships. Although

linearizing two-parameter models like the Freundlich and Langmuir equations is straightforward, the process becomes challenging for models with more than two fitting parameters. Worch (1985) showcased a method for linearizing a three-parameter nonlinear model by employing two distinct linearized forms of the model. This relatively obscure technique, also used by Marczewski et al. (1990), has proven successful in linearizing various three-parameter models, including the Sips and Toth equations.

The commonly employed linearization method for the R–P equation yields only one linearized form. An example of such a form is presented in Eq. (10), introduced in the 1980s (Allen et al., 1988). Eq. (10) implies that plotting its left-hand side against $\ln(c)$ will produce a straight line. However, prior knowledge of a is necessary, often estimated through trial and error. The fitting process involves guessing a value for a , plotting the left-hand side term against $\ln(c)$ to estimate b and n , noting the R^2 score for the linear fit, and repeating the process with a new value of a until an acceptable R^2 value is achieved. This subjective approach introduces some uncertainty into the linear regression process. Furthermore, estimating the parameters of Eq. (10) through linear regression has been found to be associated with various statistical issues, as discussed by Osmari et al. (2013). Despite these shortcomings, Eq. (10) continues to be used in recent studies (Szewczuk-Karpisz et al., 2022; Usman et al., 2022; Akiode et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2023; Mahilary and Dey, 2023).

$$\ln\left(a\frac{c}{q}-1\right)=\ln(b)+n\ln(c) \quad (10)$$

Another linearized form, as expressed in Eq. (11), was introduced in the 1990s (Juang et al., 1996). This equation advocates plotting c/q versus c^n . However, a prerequisite for a linear plot of Eq. (11) is prior knowledge of n . Similar to Eq. (10), the use of Eq. (11) for data fitting necessitates a trial-and-error approach, introducing subjective judgment into the linear regression process. Eq. (12) is a variant of Eq. (11), proposed by Wu et al. (2010). It is based on the flawed Eq. (6), where the parameter k has uncertain units when n is not equal to 1. Despite the availability of powerful computers and sophisticated data analysis software, many researchers persist in using outdated linearized forms of the R–P equation. This reliance on linearization is indefensible.

$$\frac{c}{q}=\frac{1}{a}+\frac{b}{a}c^n \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{c}{q}=\frac{1}{q_s k}+\frac{1}{q_s}c^n \quad (12)$$

Two additional linearized forms of the R–P equation merit special attention due to their incorrect structures. The first version, outlined in Eq. (13), suggests that plotting $\ln(c/q)$ against $\ln(c)$ will yield a straight line. However, this version has two flaws: (i) it omits the parameter b , and (ii) removing the logarithmic transformation from Eq. (13) results in Eq. (14), which deviates from the R–P equation [Eq. (4)]. Eq. (14) essentially becomes a Freundlich-like equation. Despite this, several recent studies have used this erroneous linearized form (Lupa et al., 2018; Mohammed et al., 2018; Singh and Bhateria, 2020; Al-Yaari and Saleh, 2022; Husna et al., 2022). The second linearized version, introduced by Ee et al. (2023) and presented in Eq. (15), is also invalid.

$$\ln\left(\frac{c}{q}\right) = -\ln(a) + n \ln(c) \quad (13)$$

$$q = \frac{ac}{c^n} = ac^{1-n} \quad (14)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{c}{q}\right) = \ln(a) + n \ln(c) \quad (15)$$

3.4. Imposing constraint on n

Redlich and Peterson (1959) stressed the importance of restricting the exponent n within the range of 0 to 1. While this guideline has been followed in many studies, there have been instances where it was overlooked. Consequently, these cases have reported values of n exceeding 1, a topic addressed by Tran et al. (2017). This section delves into the rationale behind the practice of imposing the constraint $0 < n \leq 1$.

In Fig. 4A, a synthetic dataset is shown where no apparent plateau is observed at high concentrations. The R–P equation was applied to the data without restricting the value of n . Fig. 4A shows that the fit was highly accurate, yielding an R^2 of 0.998 and a value of 0.85 for n . Similar to the Freundlich equation, the R–P equation is designed for describing data lacking a discernible plateau. Regression analyses of such data typically produce n values below 1. As a result, implementing the constraint $0 < n \leq 1$ in such cases is unnecessary.

Fig. 4. Fitting synthetic data without and with an apparent plateau with the R–P equation [Eq. (4)].

Fig. 4B illustrates a different dataset exhibiting an apparent plateau at high concentrations. The R–P equation was applied to the data without placing restrictions on n . The fit, as depicted in Fig. 4B, was almost perfect ($R^2 = 0.999$), yielding an estimated value for n exceeding 1 ($n = 1.2$). Despite the R–P equation not being explicitly designed for interpreting data with a plateau, it adeptly handles such scenarios by permitting n to exceed 1. The R–P equation was re-fitted to the Fig. 4B data with the condition $0 < n \leq 1$. The resulting fit ($R^2 = 0.984$), depicted in Fig. 4C, exhibited a decrease in accuracy compared to the previous fit in Fig. 4B. The estimated value for n was 1, indicating that the regression procedure was compelled to use the Langmuir model, contributing to the suboptimal fit observed in Fig. 4C.

From a data-fitting standpoint, the analysis outlined above indicates that there are no advantages to enforcing the constraint $0 < n \leq 1$ in the regression analysis of adsorption data, whether a plateau is present or not. When a clear plateau is evident in the data, a satisfactory fit can be achieved with the R–P equation by permitting n to go beyond 1. Regarding the Sips equation, it has the capability to predict sigmoid curves when the exponent N exceeds 1, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Some studies argue that keeping n below 1 is crucial to avoid contravening the theoretical foundations of the R–P equation. However, it is essential to emphasize that the R–P equation is an empirical model, as acknowledged by Peterson and Redlich (1962). The confusion mainly arises from the fact that the R–P equation transforms into the Langmuir model when n equals 1, leading some researchers to claim that the former equation with $n \leq 1$ has some connection to the theoretical basis of the latter model. However, the reality is that n holds no physical significance, whether it is less than or greater than 1. For practical purposes,

an n value less than 1 is necessary for accurately fitting isotherm data without a noticeable plateau. The widely held belief that enforcing the constraint $0 < n \leq 1$ is crucial in the regression of type I isotherm data is unfounded.

A related issue revolves around the behavior of the R–P equation when n assumes significantly larger values than 1. In Fig. 5, a set of curves predicted by the R–P equation for four n values (1.5, 2, 3, and 4) is depicted, with a and b held constant at 10 L g^{-1} and $0.1 \text{ L}^n \text{ mg}^{-n}$, respectively. These anomalous curves deviate from the standard isotherm curves prescribed by the IUPAC classification. Interestingly, such unconventional curve shapes have been documented in the literature.

Fig. 5. Isotherm curves predicted by the R–P equation for four n values (1.5, 2, 3, and 4), with a and b held constant at 10 L g^{-1} and $0.1 \text{ L}^n \text{ mg}^{-n}$, respectively.

Fig. 6 illustrates the application of the R–P equation to a dataset obtained from the study by Manzar et al. (2022), investigating the adsorption of tetracycline on steel slags (Mod-AR). The R–P equation fit in Fig. 6 was calculated using $a = 0.51 \text{ L g}^{-1}$, $b = 4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ L}^n \text{ mg}^{-n}$, and $n = 4.49$. Manzar et al. (2022) did not furnish an explanation for the unusual isotherm curve. It

seems that physical adsorption alone may not account for the atypical curve shape. The decline in tetracycline uptake observed at higher concentrations could be attributed to impurities present in the steel slag adsorbent, potentially catalyzing the chemical degradation of tetracycline. However, this analysis is purely speculative, and further investigation is warranted to comprehend this unusual isotherm.

Fig. 6. Fitting tetracycline adsorption data (Manzar et al., 2022) with the R–P equation [Eq. (4)].

It is worth emphasizing that the exponent n lacks physical significance, allowing it to take on negative values. A negative n permits the R–P equation to describe type III or unfavorable isotherm data, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The experimental isotherm presented in Fig. 7 was extracted from the research conducted by Hamidouche et al. (2015), describing the adsorption of 4-nitrophenol on a composite geomaterial at pH 7 and 20 °C. The R–P equation fit yielded a value of -6.18 for n , along with an R^2 of 0.990. Evidently, the R–P equation can fit type III isotherm data by allowing n to be negative. In summary, the R–P equation can generate types I and III isotherm curves, along with the atypical profile depicted in Fig. 6, which remains unclassified. Concerning the Sips equation, it predicts type I, III, and V isotherm curves.

Fig. 7. Fitting 4-nitrophenol adsorption data (Hamidouche et al., 2015) with the R–P equation [Eq. (4)].

3.5. Parameter units

There is considerable confusion surrounding the assignment of units to the two R–P parameters, a and b . The process, however, is relatively straightforward. The initial step involves choosing units for the measured quantities c and q . Typically, liquid phase concentration c is expressed in milligrams or millimoles of solute per liter of solution, while solid phase concentration q is specified in milligrams or millimoles of solute per gram of adsorbent. Subsequently, recognizing that the denominator of the ratio in Eq. (4) is unitless, we can deduce the units of a by transforming Eq. (4) into Eq. (16). Since the bc^n term must be unitless, the units of b are expressed as $1/\text{units of } c^n$, specifically $(\text{L mg}^{-1})^n$ or $(\text{mg L}^{-1})^{-n}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{units of } a &= \frac{\text{units of } q}{\text{units of } c} (\text{unitless term : } 1 + bc^n) \\
 &= \frac{\text{mg g}^{-1}}{\text{mg L}^{-1}} \\
 &= \text{L g}^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

It is concerning that many studies have mistakenly designated the units of a as L mg^{-1} , despite q being measured in units of mg g^{-1} . It is worth reiterating that in the correct units of a (L g^{-1}), the letter “g” specifically denotes the mass of the *adsorbent* in grams. Furthermore, the units of b have often been incorrectly stated as L mg^{-1} instead of the correct $(\text{L mg}^{-1})^n$. Surprisingly, even some widely cited review articles have reported the units of b as mg^{-1} (Foo

and Hameed, 2010; Al-Ghouti and Da'ana, 2020). Table 1 highlights recent instances of such errors. These careless mistakes cast a negative light on the water research community.

Table 1. Recent examples of incorrect units assigned to the R–P parameters a and b .

Parameter	Erroneous units	Ref.
a	$L\ mg^{-1}$	Diel et al. (2021); Foroutan et al. (2021); Ghahremani et al. (2021); Diaz de Tuesta et al. (2022); Jung et al. (2022); Zhang et al. (2022); Abdel-Wahed et al. (2023); El-Kholy et al. (2023); Liao et al. (2023); Wei et al. (2023)
	$mg\ L^{-1}$	Gao et al. (2022)
	$mg\ g^{-1}$	Ruello and Kim (2022)
b	$L\ mg^{-1}$	Ahmed et al. (2021); Araujo et al. (2021); Diel et al. (2021); Ghahremani et al. (2021); Nakhjiri et al. (2021); Nimbalkar and Bhat (2021); Rasoulzadeh et al. (2021); He et al. (2022); Herath et al. (2022); Liang et al. (2022); Mao et al. (2022); Martins et al. (2022); Santoso et al. (2022); Abdel-Wahed et al. (2023); Balasubramani et al. (2023); Bhat and Chisti (2023); Chen et al. (2023); El-Kholy et al. (2023); Kim et al. (2023); Wei et al. (2023); Zhang et al. (2023)
	$L\ mmol^{-1}$	Daminova et al. (2022)
	$m^3\ mg^{-1}$	Yin et al. (2022)
	$mg\ L^{-1}$	Gao et al. (2022); Jung et al. (2022); Tran and Weidhaas (2022)
	mg^{-1}	FrozandehMehr et al. (2019); Hu et al. (2019); Lazzari et al. (2021); Manikandan and Lens (2022); Saikia et al. (2022); Krajewski et al. (2023); Wang et al. (2023)
	$L\ [mg^{1-(1/a)}]^{-1}$	Ahammad et al. (2021)

3.6. Comparing R–P and Radke–Prausnitz

A prevalent modeling approach entails assessing and contrasting the data-fitting abilities of various isotherm models, often selected arbitrarily by the modeler. For meaningful comparisons, it is essential to choose models with distinct data-fitting characteristics. Unfortunately, many studies have mistakenly compared mathematically identical isotherm models, leading to modeling results that lack significance (Chu et al., 2022).

Several isotherm models, such as Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, Dubinin–Radushkevich, Sips, Toth, and Radke–Prausnitz, have been compared with the R–P equation. However, it is inappropriate to compare the R–P equation with the Radke–Prausnitz equation (Radke and Prausnitz, 1972) as they are mathematically equivalent. This similarity has recently been discussed by Diaz de Tuesta et al. (2020) and Tran et al. (2023a), but it was already noted in studies from the 1980s and 1990s. For example, Walters and Luthy (1984) mentioned that

“Radke and Prausnitz used the Redlich–Peterson equation,” and Itaya et al. (1984) referred to the Radke–Prausnitz equation used by other researchers as the R–P equation. Furthermore, Mollah and Robinson (1996) pointed out that the three-parameter isotherm (i.e., R–P) used by Mathews and Weber (1977) was similar to the empirical correlation suggested by Radke and Prausnitz (1972). In this section, a case study is presented, delving into the mathematical equivalence between the R–P and Radke–Prausnitz equations.

Eq. (17) represents the original form of the empirical correlation introduced by Radke and Prausnitz (1972), featuring fitting parameters α , β , and m . As highlighted by the authors, at low concentrations, Eq. (17) converges to Henry’s law, while at higher concentrations, it transforms into the Freundlich isotherm. Additionally, when m equals 0, the Langmuir isotherm emerges from Eq. (17). These attributes align with those of the R–P equation.

$$\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{\alpha c} + \frac{1}{\beta c^m} \quad (17)$$

By manipulating Eq. (17), we obtain Eqs. (18) and (19), which take on the conventional forms of isotherm models. A comparison between the R–P equation [Eq. (4)] and the Radke–Prausnitz equation [Eq. (18)] reveals their similarity. Setting $\alpha = a$, $\alpha/\beta = b$, and $m = 1 - n$, Eq. (4) can be readily derived from Eq. (18). Hence, the Radke–Prausnitz equation is formally equivalent to the R–P equation. Unfortunately, Radke and Prausnitz (1972) opted to present their model in the form of Eq. (17) rather than Eq. (18), making it somewhat challenging to discern its resemblance to the R–P equation.

$$q = \frac{\alpha c}{1 + (\alpha/\beta) c^{1-m}} \quad (18)$$

$$q = \frac{\beta c^m}{1 + (\beta/\alpha) c^{m-1}} \quad (19)$$

By applying the R–P equation to experimental data, the values of a , b , and n can be determined, and the aforementioned parameter relationships can then be used to calculate the Radke–Prausnitz parameters. This allows for the determination of α , β , and m without necessitating the fitting of the Radke–Prausnitz equation to the same dataset. To illustrate this process, a recently published dataset concerning the adsorption of sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate on TiO₂ nanoparticles (Xu et al., 2022) was fitted to the R–P equation, resulting in $a = 9.86 \text{ L g}^{-1}$, $b = 1.15 \text{ L}^n \text{ mg}^{-n}$, and $n = 0.57$. By substituting these fitted values into the parameter relationships, the three Radke–Prausnitz parameters were determined ($\alpha = a = 9.86 \text{ L g}^{-1}$, $\beta = \alpha/b = 9.86/1.15 = 8.57 \text{ mg}^{1-m} \text{ L}^m \text{ g}^{-1}$, and $m = 1 - n = 1 - 0.57 = 0.43$). To validate

these values, the Radke–Prausnitz equation was also applied to the same isotherm data, yielding practically identical values of $\alpha = 9.86 \text{ L g}^{-1}$, $\beta = 8.54 \text{ mg}^{1-m} \text{ L}^m \text{ g}^{-1}$, and $m = 0.43$. Both fits, as depicted in Fig. 8, produced the same R^2 value of 0.997.

Fig. 8. Fitting sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate adsorption data (Xu et al., 2022) with the R–P equation [Eq. (4)] (A) and the Radke–Prausnitz equation [Eq. (18)] (B).

In essence, the Radke–Prausnitz and R–P equations yield identical fits to a given dataset, as they are mathematically equivalent. Therefore, any attempt to compare these equations in data correlation amounts to a meaningless curve-fitting exercise. Notably, despite being featured in several review articles (Foo and Hameed, 2010; Saadi et al., 2015; Majd et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2023), none of these sources acknowledge the equivalence between these equations.

3.7. Model misidentification

In certain studies, the R–P equation [Eq. (4)] has been erroneously labeled as the Jossens isotherm. The root of this misattribution can be traced back to articles from the 1980s. While the pioneering work of Jossens et al. (1978) correctly credited Redlich and Peterson’s original work as the source for Eq. (4), McKay et al. (1985,1987) inadvertently misattributed the origin of the R–P equation to Jossens et al. (1978). This misattribution has persisted for nearly four decades, as evident in some recent publications that still refer to the R–P equation as the Jossens isotherm (Hashem et al., 2021; Beig et al., 2023; Zeghioud and Mouhamadou, 2023).

3.8. Thermodynamic calculations

Determining thermodynamic properties, such as the standard adsorption Gibbs energy ΔG° , the standard adsorption enthalpy ΔH° , and the standard adsorption entropy ΔS° , is a key focus in adsorption research. These thermodynamic parameters are commonly obtained through Eqs. (20) and (21), where K° is a dimensionless quantity representing the thermodynamic equilibrium constant, R denotes the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln(K^\circ) \quad (20)$$

$$\ln(K^\circ) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} \quad (21)$$

In the context of a dilute solution containing a non-ionic solute, it is commonly assumed that the activity coefficient is equal to 1 (Salvestrini and Bollinger, 2022). This assumption leads to the definition of K° as expressed in Eq. (22), where K_{iso} represents an equilibrium constant derived from the selected isotherm model and C° denotes the standard solute concentration. Usually, the chosen standard state for the solute is $C^\circ = 1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Consequently, it is necessary to express K_{iso} in L mol^{-1} to ensure that K° is unitless.

$$K^\circ = K_{iso} C^\circ \quad (22)$$

Deriving the three thermodynamic parameters from Eqs. (20)–(22) necessitates obtaining K_{iso} values at different temperatures. Unfortunately, deriving K_{iso} from the R–P equation is not feasible due to the inability to express its parameters, a and b , in units of L mol^{-1} . When c and q are expressed in mol L^{-1} and mol kg^{-1} , respectively, the units for a and b become L kg^{-1} and $(\text{L mol}^{-1})^n$, respectively. It is apparent that a cannot be considered an equilibrium constant, as the unit “kg” denotes the adsorbent mass. The inclusion of the exponent n in the units of b precludes the direct substitution of this parameter for K_{iso} in Eq. (22). Therefore, the thermodynamic parameters calculated from Eqs. (20)–(22) using either a or b as K_{iso} , as reported in certain recent studies (Vu et al., 2018; Oumani et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020), lack physical significance.

A workaround was concocted to reconcile the units of b $[(\text{L mol}^{-1})^n]$ with those of K_{iso} (L mol^{-1}), as depicted in Eq. (23) (Tran et al., 2023b). While Eq. (23) facilitates the use of b to calculate K_{iso} , it is essential to recognize that K_{iso} , or the modified b , may deviate from accurately fitting the isotherm data originally used to determine the initial b . Various alternative isotherm models provide equilibrium constants with appropriate units (L mol^{-1}) for use as K_{iso}

in Eq. (22). As a result, there is no compelling necessity to use the R–P equation in thermodynamic calculations.

$$K_{iso} = \sqrt[n]{b} \quad (23)$$

4. Conclusions

The R–P equation has encountered widespread misuse and misinterpretation, resulting in the publication of numerous modeling studies with questionable quality. This has significantly tarnished the literature, creating a risk of leading novice researchers astray. To navigate these challenges, modelers are advised to follow specific guidelines, including:

- When fitting experimental data, opt for the original expression specified in Eq. (4) rather than the Langmuir-like expression presented in Eq. (6), as the k parameter in the latter has ambiguous units.
- Avoid making mechanistic inferences based solely on a successful fit of the R–P equation to experimental data, given its entirely empirical nature and lack of a clear physical basis.
- Steer clear of using the outdated linearized versions presented in Eqs. (10) and (11) to fit experimental data, as they require a trial-and-error approach. Additionally, avoid the erroneous linearized versions described in Eqs. (13) and (15).
- Disregard the requirement for the exponent n to be confined within the range of 0–1. As n is an empirical parameter, there is no solid theoretical justification for constraining it within this range. When n falls within the 0–1 range, the R–P equation predicts type I curve shapes. When n falls outside the 0–1 range, the R–P equation projects other curve shapes.
- Avoid assigning incorrect units to the R–P parameters a and b . When c and q are expressed in mg L^{-1} and mg g^{-1} , respectively, a and b assume the units of L g^{-1} and $(\text{L mg}^{-1})^n$, respectively.
- Refrain from comparing the R–P and Radke–Prausnitz equations in data correlation, as they are mathematically equivalent and should yield identical results when fitted to a specific dataset.
- Do not refer to Eq. (4) as the Jossens isotherm, as this is a case of misidentification.
- Avoid using the R–P parameters (a and b) to calculate thermodynamic properties, as they do not represent true equilibrium constants.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abdel-Wahed, M.S., El-Kalliny, A.S., Shehata, F.A., Abd El-Aty, A.M., Gad-Allah, T.A., 2023. One-pot green synthesis of magnetic adsorbent via *Anabaena sphaerica* and its performance towards Remazol Red dye removal from aqueous media. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 279, 118939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2023.118939>.
- Abdulkareem, A.S., Hamzat, W.A., Tijani, J.O., Egbosiuba, T.C., Mustapha, S., Abubakre, O.K., Okafor, B.O., Babayemi, A.K., 2023. Isotherm, kinetics, thermodynamics and mechanism of metal ions adsorption from electroplating wastewater using treated and functionalized carbon nanotubes. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 109180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.109180>.
- Ahammad, N.A., Zulkifli, M.A., Ahmad, M.A., Hameed, B.H., Mohd Din, A.T., 2021. Desorption of chloramphenicol from ordered mesoporous carbon-alginate beads: effects of operating parameters, and isotherm, kinetics, and regeneration studies. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.105015>.
- Ahmed, W., Mehmood, S., Qaswar, M., Ali, S., Khan, Z.H., Ying, H., Chen, D.-Y., Núñez-Delgado, A., 2021. Oxidized biochar obtained from rice straw as adsorbent to remove uranium (VI) from aqueous solutions. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105104>.
- Akiode, O.K., Adetoro, A., Anene, A.I., Afolabi, S.O., Alli, Y.A., 2023. Methodical study of chromium (VI) ion adsorption from aqueous solution using low-cost agro-waste material: isotherm, kinetic, and thermodynamic studies. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 30, 48036–48047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-25706-1>.
- Al-Ghouti, M.A., Da'ana, D.A., 2020. Guidelines for the use and interpretation of adsorption isotherm models: a review. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 393, 122383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.122383>.

- Allen, S.J., McKay, G., Khader, K.Y.H., 1988. Multi-component sorption isotherms of basic dyes onto peat. *Environ. Pollut.* 52, 39–53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0269-7491\(88\)90106-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0269-7491(88)90106-6).
- Al-Yaari, M., Saleh, T.A., 2022. Mercury removal from water using a novel composite of polyacrylate-modified carbon. *ACS Omega* 7, 14820–14831. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c00274>.
- Araujo, L.A., Bezerra, C.O., Cusioli, L.F., Rodríguez, M.T., Gomes, R.G., Bergamasco, R., 2021. Diclofenac adsorption using a low-cost adsorbent derived from *Guazuma ulmifolia* Lam. fruit via chemical and thermal treatment. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 106629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106629>.
- Balasubramani, K., Sivarajasekar, N., Sarojini, G., Naushad, Mu., 2023. Removal of antidiabetic pharmaceutical (metformin) using graphene oxide microcrystalline cellulose (GOMCC): insights to process optimization, equilibrium, kinetics, and machine learning. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 62, 4713–4728. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c04480>.
- Bedadeep, D., Shahnaz, T., Sankar, V.M., Sahoo, L., Narayanasamy, S., 2023. Organic polymer doped graphene-based composite for the effective elimination of diclofenac: a detailed study with phytotoxic assessments. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 109223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.109223>.
- Beig, S.U.R., Shah, S.A., 2023. Adsorption of Cr(VI) by NaOH-modified microporous activated carbons derived from the wastes of *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Magnolia soulangeana*, and *Tanacetum Vulgar* L.: mechanism, isotherms, and kinetic studies. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 30, 35808–35837. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-24616-y>.
- Belkassa, K., Khelifa, M., Batonneau-Gener, I., Marouf-Khelifa, K., Khelifa, A., 2021. Understanding of the mechanism of crystal violet adsorption on modified halloysite: hydrophobicity, performance, and interaction. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 415, 125656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.125656>.
- Bhat, A.H., Chisti, H.-T.-N., 2023. Fabrication of versatile Ag-P/PPy core-shell nanocomposite: adsorption efficacy for chromium (VI) removal and assessment of antioxidant and antibacterial activities. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 110664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110664>.
- Boubaker, H., Arfi, R.B., Mougin, K., Vaultot, C., Hajjar, S., Kunneman, P., Schrodj, G., Ghorbal, A., 2021. New optimization approach for successive cationic and anionic dyes uptake using reed-based beads. *J. Clean. Prod.* 307, 127218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127218>.

- Brião, G.D.V., Hashim, M.A., Chu, K.H., 2023. The Sips isotherm equation: often used and sometimes misused. *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 58, 884–892. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2023.2167662>.
- Chaparro, T.D.C., Silva, R.D., Monteiro, I.S., Barros-Timmons, A., Giudici, R., Martins dos Santos, A., Bourgeat-Lami, E., 2019. Interaction of cationic, anionic, and nonionic macroraft homo- and copolymers with laponite clay. *Langmuir* 35, 11512–11523. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.9b01987>.
- Cheknane, B., Zermane, F., Bouras, O., Debord, J., Harel, M., Bollinger, J.-C., Sellaoui, L., Bonilla-Petriciolet, A., 2021. Modeling of binary and ternary batch adsorption systems via multidimensional logistic distribution and statistical physics. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105664>.
- Chen, J. Lu, J., Jiang, S.Y., Lee, C.H., Li, Y., Ruan, H.D., 2023. The effect of modifier adding sequence on physical-chemical property and adsorption ability of Inorganic-Organic Montmorillonite (IOMMt). *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 110115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110115>.
- Chu, K.H., Debord, J., Harel, M., Bollinger, J.-C., 2022. Mirror, mirror on the wall, which is the fairest of them all? Comparing the Hill, Sips, Koble–Corrigan, and Liu adsorption isotherms. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61, 6781–6790, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c00507>.
- Daminova, S.S., Kadirova, Z.C., Sharipov, K.T., Sanaqulov, Q.S., Rakhmonova, D.S., Miyauchi, M., Sugai, Y., Czech, B., Hojamberdiev, M., 2022. Elucidating the crystal structure-dependent Cd²⁺-uptake property of benzimidazolium ionic liquid immobilized into macroporous polystyrene. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 108900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108900>.
- Diaz de Tuesta, J.L., Silva, A.M.T., Faria, J.L., Gomes, H.T., 2020. Adsorption of Sudan-IV contained in oily wastewater on lipophilic activated carbons: kinetic and isotherm modeling. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 27, 20770–20785. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-08473-1>.
- Diaz de Tuesta, J.L., Roman, F.F., Marques, V.C., Silva, A.S., Silva, A.P.F., Bosco, T.C., Shinibekova, A.A., Aknur, S., Kalmakhanova, M.S., Massalimova, B.K., Arrobas, M., Silva, A.M.T., Gomes, H.T., 2022. Performance and modeling of Ni(II) adsorption from low concentrated wastewater on carbon microspheres prepared from tangerine peels by FeCl₃-assisted hydrothermal carbonization. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 108143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108143>.

- Diel, J.C., Franco, D.S.P., Nunes, I.D.S., Pereira, H.A., Moreira, K.S., Burgo, T.A.D.L., Foletto, E.L., Dotto, G.L., 2021. Carbon nanotubes impregnated with metallic nanoparticles and their application as an adsorbent for the glyphosate removal in an aqueous matrix. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105178>.
- Ee, L.Y., Chia, S.Y.R., Xue, K., Chin, S.Y., Cho, C.A.H., Tan, X.Y., Li, S.F.Y., 2023. Hyperbranched nanocellulose enabling rapid boron removal from aqueous environment. *Chem. Eng. J.* 454, 140218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.140218>.
- El-Kholy, S.A., Radwan, E.K., El-Naggar, M.E., El-Wakeel, S.T., El Sayed, I.E.T., 2023. Sponge-like zinc oxide nanoparticles loaded xanthan gum/cationic chitosan cryogel: synthesis, characterization, microbicidal and adsorption of synthetic dye and heavy metal. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 110652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110652>.
- Foo, K.Y., Hameed, B.H., 2010. Insights into the modeling of adsorption isotherm systems. *Chem. Eng. J.* 156, 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2009.09.013>.
- Foroutan, R., Peighambaroust, S.J., Latifi, P., Ahmadi, A., Alizadeh, M., Ramavandi, B., 2021. Carbon nanotubes/ β -cyclodextrin/ MnFe_2O_4 as a magnetic nanocomposite powder for tetracycline antibiotic decontamination from different aqueous environments. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 106344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106344>.
- FrozandehMehr, E., Tarlani, A., Farhadi, S., 2019. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) bloated micelles and merged CTAB/bolaamphiphiles self-assembled vesicles toward the generation of highly porous alumina as efficacious inorganic adsorbents. *Langmuir* 35, 11188–11199. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.9b01934>.
- Gao, G., Xie, S., Zheng, S., Xu, Y., Sun, Y., 2022. Two-step modification (sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate composites acid-base) of sepiolite (SDBS/ABsep) and its performance for remediation of Cd contaminated water and soil. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 433, 128760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128760>.
- Ge, Q., Tian, Q., Wang, S., Zhang, J., Hou, R., 2022. Highly efficient removal of lead/cadmium by phosphoric acid-modified hydrochar prepared from fresh banana peels: adsorption mechanisms and environmental application. *Langmuir* 38, 15394–15403. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.2c02693>.
- Ghahremani, P., Vakili, M.H., Nezamzadeh-Ejehieh, A., 2021. Optimization of Pb(II) removal by a novel modified silica aerogel using Quince seed mucilage with response surface methodology. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 106648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106648>.

- Gómez-Avilés, A., Peñas-Garzón, M., Belver, C., Rodríguez, J.J., Bedia, J., 2022. Equilibrium, kinetics and breakthrough curves of acetaminophen adsorption onto activated carbons from microwave-assisted FeCl₃-activation of lignin. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 278, 119654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2021.119654>.
- Hamidouche, S., Bouras, O., Zermane, F., Cheknane, B., Houari, M., Debord, J., Harel, M., Bollinger, J.-C., Baudu, M., 2015. Simultaneous sorption of 4-nitrophenol and 2-nitrophenol on a hybrid geocomposite based on surfactant-modified pillared-clay and activated carbon. *Chem. Eng. J.* 279, 964–972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.05.012>.
- Hashem, A., Taha, G.M., Fletcher, A.J., Mohamed, L.A., Samaha, S.H., 2021. Highly efficient adsorption of Cd(II) onto carboxylated camelthorn biomass: applicability of three-parameter isotherm models, kinetics, and mechanism. *J. Polym. Environ.* 29, 1630–1642. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-020-01991-6>.
- He, M., Ng, T.C.A., Huang, S., Xu, B., Ng, H.Y., 2022. Ammonium removal and recovery from effluent of AnMBR treating real domestic wastewater using polymeric hydrogel. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 296, 121376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.121376>.
- Herath, A., Salehi, M., Jansone-Popova, S., 2022. Production of polyacrylonitrile/ionic covalent organic framework hybrid nanofibers for effective removal of chromium(VI) from water. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 427, 128167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.128167>.
- Hu, C., Xu, W., Li, H., Zhou, S., Mo, X., Zhang, P., Tang, K., 2019. Highly efficient adsorption of Au(III) from water by a novel metal–organic framework constructed with sulfur-containing ligands and Zn(II). *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 58, 17972–17979. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b03433>.
- Hu, Q., Lan, R., He, L., Liu, H., Pei, X., 2023. A critical review of adsorption isotherm models for aqueous contaminants: curve characteristics, site energy distribution and common controversies. *J. Environ. Manage.* 329, 117104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.117104>.
- Husna, M.Y.N., Chong, C.H., Wong, V.-L., Cheah, K.H., Wan, Y.K., 2022. 3D-printed PEGDA monolith with robust silane-grafted chitosan for enhanced textile wastewater treatment. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 108581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108581>.
- Inglezakis, V.J., Fyrrillas, M.M., Park, J., 2019. Variable diffusivity homogeneous surface diffusion model and analysis of merits and fallacies of simplified adsorption kinetics equations. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 367, 224–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.12.023>.

- Itaya, A., Kato, N., Yamamoto, J., Okamoto, K., 1984. Liquid phase adsorption equilibrium of phenol and its derivatives on macroreticular adsorbents. *J. Chem. Eng. Jpn.* 17, 389–395. <https://doi.org/10.1252/jcej.17.389>.
- Joshi, M., Kremling, A., Seidel-Morgenstern, A., 2006. Model based statistical analysis of adsorption equilibrium data. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 61, 7805–7818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2006.08.052>.
- Jossens, L., Prausnitz, J.M., Fritz, W., Schlünder, E.U., Myers, A.L., 1978. Thermodynamics of multi-solute adsorption from dilute aqueous solutions. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 33, 1097–1106. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509\(78\)85015-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509(78)85015-5).
- Juang, R.-S., Wu, F.-C., Tseng, R.-L., 1996. Adsorption isotherms of phenolic compounds from aqueous solutions onto activated carbon fibers. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 41, 487–492. <https://doi.org/10.1021/je950238g>.
- Jung, Y., Do, T., Choi, U.S., Jung, K.-W., Choi, J.-W., 2022. Cage-like amine-rich polymeric capsule with internal 3D center-radial channels for efficient and selective gold recovery. *Chem. Eng. J.* 438, 135618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.135618>.
- Khaledi, K., Labrada, G.V., Soltan, J., Predicala, B., Nemati, M., 2021. Adsorptive removal of tetracycline and lincomycin from contaminated water using magnetized activated carbon. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105998>.
- Kim, H.-N., Kim, J.-H., Lee, K.J., Kim, I., Yoon, I.-H., 2023. Enhanced removal of cesium from hydrobiotite using polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based nickel ferrocyanide beads. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 452, 131360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.131360>.
- Kinniburgh, D.G., 1986. General purpose adsorption isotherms. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 20, 895–904. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es00151a008>.
- Krajewski, M., Pietrzyk, P., Osial, M., Liou, S.-C., Kubacki, J., 2023. Iron–iron oxide core–shell nanochains as high-performance adsorbents of crystal violet and congo red dyes from aqueous solutions. *Langmuir* 39, 8367–8377. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.3c00967>.
- Kumar, M., Mukherjee, S., Thakur, A.K., Raval, N., An, A.K., Gikas, P., 2022. Aminoalkyl-organosilane treated sand for the adsorptive removal of arsenic from the groundwater: immobilizing the mobilized geogenic contaminants. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 425, 127916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127916>.
- Lazzari, L.K., Perondi, D., Zattera, A.J., Santana, R.M.C., 2021. Cellulose/biochar cryogels: a study of adsorption kinetics and isotherms. *Langmuir* 37, 3180–3188. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.1c00123>.

- Lee, R.G., Weber, T.W., 1969. Interpretation of methane adsorption on activated carbon by nonisothermal and isothermal calculations. *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 47, 60–65. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.5450470111>.
- Lee, E.Y., Wong, S.Y., Phang, S.J., Wong, V.-L., Cheah, K.H., 2023. Additively manufactured photoreactor with immobilized thermoset acrylic-graphitic carbon nitride nanosheets for water remediation: response surface methods and adsorption modelling studies. *Chem. Eng. J.* 455, 140633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.140633>.
- Li, Y., Wen, J., Xue, Z., Yin, X., Yuan, L., Yang, C., 2022. Removal of Cr(VI) by polyaniline embedded polyvinyl alcohol/sodium alginate beads – extension from water treatment to soil remediation. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 426, 127809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127809>.
- Liang, C., Qin, S., Ai, H., Li, S., Du, K., 2022. Novel amyloid-like porous lysozyme skeletons as “green” superadsorbent presenting ultrahigh capacity and rapid sequestration towards hazardous Congo red. *Chem. Eng. J.* 441, 136005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.136005>.
- Liao, J., He, X., Zhang, Y., Zhang, L., He, Z., 2023. The construction of magnetic hydroxyapatite-functionalized pig manure-derived biochar for the efficient uranium separation. *Chem. Eng. J.* 457, 141367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.141367>.
- Lupa, L., Cochechi, L., Pode, R., Hulka, I., 2018. Phenol adsorption using Aliquat 336 functionalized Zn-Al layered double hydroxide. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 196, 82–95. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2017.10.003>.
- Madeira, L., Almeida, A., da Costa, A.M.R., Mestre, A.S., Carvalho, F., Teixeira, M.R., 2023. Tuning processes for organic matter removal from slaughterhouse wastewater treated by immediate one-step lime precipitation and atmospheric carbonation. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 110450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110450>.
- Mahilary, H.K., Dey, A.K., 2023. Preparation and application of carboxylated and mechanically attrited carbon for adsorptive removal of crystal violet dye. *Environ. Sci. Water Res. Technol.* 9, 861–882. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ew00723a>.
- Majd, M.M., Kordzadeh-Kermani, V., Ghalandari, V., Askari, A., Sillanpää, M., 2022. Adsorption isotherm models: a comprehensive and systematic review (2010–2020). *Sci. Total Environ.* 812, 151334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151334>.
- Mangwandi, C., Chen, H., Wu, J., 2022. Production and optimization of adsorbent materials from teawaste for heavy metal removal from aqueous solution: feasibility of hexavalent

- chromium removal – kinetics, thermodynamics and isotherm study. *Water Pract. Technol.* 17, 1866–1880. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2022.105>.
- Manikandan, N.A., Lens, P.N., 2022. Biorefining of green macroalgal (*Ulva* sp.) biomass and its application in the adsorptive recovery of rare earth elements (REEs). *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 303, 122200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.122200>.
- Manzar, M.S., Ahmad, T., Ullah, N., Chellam, P.V., John, J., Zubair, M., Brandão, R.J., Meili, L., Alagha, O., Çevik, E., 2022. Comparative adsorption of eriochrome black T and tetracycline by NaOH-modified steel dust: kinetic and process modeling. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 287, 120559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.120559>.
- Mao, C., Sang, H., Chen, Y., Wei, Y., Wu, Y., 2022. Layer-by-layer grafting synthesis of silicon-based zirconium organophosphate for the enhanced and selective adsorption of lanthanides. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 108608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108608>.
- Marczewski, A.W., Deryło-Marczewska, A., Jaroniec, M., 1990. A simple method for evaluating the isotherm parameters for adsorption from dilute solutions on solids. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 24, 287–297. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0254-0584\(90\)90092-O](https://doi.org/10.1016/0254-0584(90)90092-O).
- Martins, L.R., Soares, L.C., Gurgel, L.V.A., Gil, L.F., 2022. Use of a new zwitterionic cellulose derivative for removal of crystal violet and orange II from aqueous solutions. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 424, 127401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127401>.
- Mathews, A.P., Weber Jr., W.J., 1977. Effects of external mass transfer and intraparticle diffusion on adsorption in slurry reactors. *AIChE Symp. Ser.* 73, 91–98.
- McKay, G., Otterburn, M.S., Aga, J.A., 1985. Fuller's earth and fired clay as adsorbents for dyestuffs. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 24, 307–322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00292065>.
- McKay, G., El Geundi, M., Nassar, M.M., 1987. Equilibrium studies during the removal of dyestuffs from aqueous solutions using bagasse pith. *Water Res.* 21, 1513–1520. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(87\)90135-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(87)90135-7).
- Meyer, O.A., Weber, T.W., 1967. Nonisothermal adsorption in fixed beds. *AIChE J.* 13, 457–465. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690130314>.
- Mohammed, B.B., Yamni, K., Tijani, N., Alrashdi, A.A., Zouihri, H., Dehmani, Y., Chung, I.-M., Kim, S.-H., Lgaz, H., 2019. Adsorptive removal of phenol using faujasite-type Y zeolite: adsorption isotherms, kinetics and grand canonical Monte Carlo simulation studies. *J. Mol. Liq.* 296, 111997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2019.111997>.

- Mollah, A.H., Robinson, C.W., 1996. Pentachlorophenol adsorption and desorption characteristics of granular activated carbon—I. Isotherms. *Water Res.* 30, 2901–2906. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(96\)00131-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(96)00131-5).
- Mudhoo, A., Pittman Jr., C.U., 2023. Adsorption data modeling and analysis under scrutiny: a clarion call to redress recently found troubling flaws. *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 192, 371–388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2023.02.033>.
- Nakhjiri, M.T., Marandi, G.B., Kurdtabar, M., 2021. Preparation of magnetic double network nanocomposite hydrogel for adsorption of phenol and p-nitrophenol from aqueous solution. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105039. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105039>.
- Nimbalkar, M.N., Bhat, B.R., 2021. Simultaneous adsorption of methylene blue and heavy metals from water using Zr-MOF having free carboxylic group. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 106216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106216>.
- Osmari, T.A., Gallon, R., Schwaab, M., Barbosa-Coutinho, E., Severo Jr, J.B., Pinto, J.C., 2013. Statistical analysis of linear and non-linear regression for the estimation of adsorption isotherm parameters. *Adsorpt. Sci. Technol.* 31, 433–458. <https://doi.org/10.1260/0263-6174.31.5.433>.
- Oumani, A., Mandi, L., Berrekhis, F., Ouazzani, N., 2019. Removal of Cr³⁺ from tanning effluents by adsorption onto phosphate mine waste: key parameters and mechanisms. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 378 (2019) 120718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.05.111>.
- Peterson, D.L., Redlich, O., 1962. Sorption of normal paraffins by molecular sieves type 5A. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 7, 570–574. <https://doi.org/10.1021/je60015a043>.
- Radke, C.J., Prausnitz, J.M., 1972. Adsorption of organic solutes from dilute aqueous solution of activated carbon. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Fundam.* 11, 445–451. <https://doi.org/10.1021/i160044a003>.
- Rasoulzadeh, H., Sheikhmohammadi, A., Abtahi, M., Roshan, B., Jokar, R., 2021. Eco-friendly rapid removal of palladium from aqueous solutions using alginate-diatomite magnano composite. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9, 105954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105954>.
- Redlich, O., Peterson, D.L., 1959. A useful adsorption isotherm. *J. Phys. Chem.* 63, 1024–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1021/j150576a611>.
- Reif-Acherman, S., 2008. Otto Redlich: chemist and gentleman from the “old school”, *Quím. Nova* 31, 1901–1908. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-40422008000700053>.
- Repo, E., Petrus, R., Sillanpää, M., Warchoł, J.K., 2011. Equilibrium studies on the adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) by modified silica gels: one-component and binary systems. *Chem. Eng. J.* 172, 376–385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2011.06.019>.

- Rouibah, K., Ferkous, H., Delimi, A., Himeur, T., Benamira, M., Zighed, M., Darwish, A.S., Lemaoui, T., Yadav, K.K., Bhutto, J.K., Ahmad, A., Chaiprapat, S., Benguerba, Y., 2023. Biosorption of zinc (II) from synthetic wastewater by using *Inula Viscosa* leaves as a low-cost biosorbent: experimental and molecular modeling studies. *J. Environ. Manage.* 326, 116742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116742>.
- Ruello, J.L.A., Kim, H., 2022. Microwave-induced fabrication of fiber-reinforced adsorbent from waste cardboard and chitosan for effective dye removal. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 108724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108724>.
- Saadi, R., Saadi, Z., Fazaeli, R., Fard, N.E., 2015. Monolayer and multilayer adsorption isotherm models for sorption from aqueous media. *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 32, 787–799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-015-0053-7>.
- Saikia, S., Sinharoy, A., Lens, P.N., 2022. Adsorptive removal of gallium from aqueous solution onto biogenic elemental tellurium nanoparticles. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 286, 120462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.120462>.
- Salvestrini, S., Bollinger, J.-C., 2022. Revisiting the extended van't Hoff equation: comments on “Highly-efficient nitrogen self-doped biochar for versatile dyes’ removal prepared from soybean cake via a simple dual-templating approach and associated thermodynamics”. *J. Clean. Prod.* 373, 133632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133632>.
- Santoso, S.P., Angkawijaya, A.E., Bundjaja, V., Kurniawan, A., Yuliana, M., Hsieh, C.-W., Go, A.W., Cheng, K.-C., Soetaredjo, F.E., Ismadji, S., 2022. Investigation of the influence of crosslinking activation methods on the physicochemical and Cu(II) adsorption characteristics of cellulose hydrogels. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10, 106971. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106971>.
- Schwaab, M., Steffani, E., Barbosa-Coutinho, E., Severo Júnior, J.B., 2017. Critical analysis of adsorption/diffusion modelling as a function of time square root. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 173, 179–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2017.07.037>.
- Singh, R., Bhatia, R., 2020. Optimization and experimental design of the Pb²⁺ adsorption process on a nano-Fe₃O₄-based adsorbent using the response surface methodology. *ACS Omega* 5, 28305–28318. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c04284>.
- Singh, R., Datta, B., 2022. Banana peel powder as an effective multilayer adsorbent of ammonium ions. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61, 18464–18474. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c03052>.
- Sips, R., 1948. On the structure of a catalyst surface. *J. Chem. Phys.* 16, 490–495. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1746922>.

- Song, D.I., Shin, W.S., 2005. Three-parameter empirical isotherm model: its application to sorption onto organoclays. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 39, 1138–1143. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es048800n>.
- Szewczuk-Karpisz, K., Bajda, T., Tomczyk, A., Kuśmierz, M., Komaniecka, I., 2022. Immobilization mechanism of $\text{Cd}^{2+}/\text{HCrO}_4^-/\text{CrO}_4^{2-}$ ions and carboxin on montmorillonite modified with *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *trifolii* exopolysaccharide. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 428, 128228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128228>.
- Tran, D., Weidhaas, J., 2022. Ion exchange for effective separation of 3-nitro-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (NTO) from wastewater. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 436, 129215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129215>.
- Tran, H.N., You, S.-J., Hosseini-Bandegharai, A., Chao, H.-P., 2017. Mistakes and inconsistencies regarding adsorption of contaminants from aqueous solutions: a critical review. *Water Res.* 120, 88–116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.04.014>.
- Tran, H.N., Bollinger, J.-C., Salvestrini, S., Chu, K.H., Juang, R.-S., 2023a. Critical review and discussion of the nonlinear form of Radke–Prausnitz model in adsorption solid–liquid phases. *J. Environ. Eng.* 149, 03122006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/10.1061/JOEEDU.EEENG-7074>.
- Tran, H.N., Thanh Trung, N.P., Lima, E.C., Bollinger, J.-C., Dat, N.D., Chao, H.-P., Juang, R.-S., 2023b. Revisiting the calculation of thermodynamic parameters of adsorption processes from the modified equilibrium constant of the Redlich–Peterson model. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 98, 462–472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.7258>.
- Trudgill, P., 1998. The meanings of words should not be allowed to vary or change, in: Bauer, L., Trudgill P., (Eds.), *Language Myths*, Penguin Books, London, pp. 1–8.
- Usman, U.L., Allam, B.K., Singh, N.B., Banerjee, S., 2022. Adsorptive removal of Cr(VI) from wastewater by hexagonal boron nitride-magnetite nanocomposites: kinetics, mechanism and LCA analysis. *J. Mol. Liq.* 354, 118833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.118833>.
- Vargas, A.M.M., Cazetta, A.L., Martins, A.C., Moraes, J.C.G., Garcia, E.E., Gauze, G.F., Costa, W.F., Almeida, V.C., 2012. Kinetic and equilibrium studies: adsorption of food dyes Acid Yellow 6, Acid Yellow 23, and Acid Red 18 on activated carbon from flamboyant pods. *Chem. Eng. J.* 181–182, 243–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2011.11.073>.
- Vu, M.T., Chao, H.-P., Van Trinh, T., Le, T.T., Lin, C.-C., Tran, H.N., 2018. Removal of ammonium from groundwater using NaOH-treated activated carbon derived from corncob

- wastes: batch and column experiments. *J. Clean. Prod.* 180, 560–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.01.104>.
- Walters, R.W., Luthy, R.G., 1984. Equilibrium adsorption of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons from water onto activated carbon. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 18, 395–403. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es00124a002>.
- Wang, B., Ma, Y., Xu, W., Tang, K., 2023. A novel S,N-rich MOF for efficient recovery of Au(III): performance and mechanism. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 451, 131051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.131051>.
- Wei, T., Wu, H., Li, Z., 2023. Lignin immobilized cyclodextrin composite microspheres with multifunctionalized surface chemistry for non-competitive adsorption of co-existing endocrine disruptors in water. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 441, 129969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129969>.
- Worch, E., 1985. Untersuchungen zur Einzel- und Gemischadsorption von Phenolen an Aktivkohlen. Teil 1. Einzeladsorptionsgleichgewichte von Phenol, p-Chlorphenol und p-Nitrophenol. *Acta hydrochim. Hydrobiol.* 13, 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ahch.19850130116>.
- Wu, F.-C., Liu, B.-L., Wu, K.-T., Tseng, R.-L., 2010. A new linear form analysis of Redlich–Peterson isotherm equation for the adsorptions of dyes. *Chem. Eng. J.* 162, 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2010.03.006>.
- Xiao, Y., Azaiez, J., Hill, J.M., 2018. Erroneous application of pseudo-second-order adsorption kinetics model: ignored assumptions and spurious correlations. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 57, 2705–2709. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.7b04724>.
- Xu, R., Li, Q., Liao, L., Wu, Z., Yin, Z., Yang, Y., Jiang, T., 2022. Simultaneous and efficient removal of multiple heavy metal(loid)s from aqueous solutions using Fe/Mn (hydr)oxide and phosphate mineral composites synthesized by regulating the proportion of Fe(II), Fe(III), Mn(II) and PO_4^{3-} . *J. Hazard. Mater.* 438, 129481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129481>.
- Yin, Q., Nie, Y., Han, Y., Wang, R. and Zhao, Z., 2022. Properties and the application of sludge-based biochar in the removal of phosphate and methylene blue from water: effects of acid treating. *Langmuir* 38, 1833–1844. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.1c02946>.
- Zeghioud, H., Mouhamadou, S., 2023. Dye removal characteristics of magnetic biochar derived from sewage sludge: isotherm, thermodynamics, kinetics, and mechanism. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 234, 233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06251-6>.

- Zhang, L., He, F., Mao, W., Guan, Y., 2020. Fast and efficient removal of Cr(VI) to ppb level together with Cr(III) sequestration in water using layered double hydroxide intercalated with diethyldithiocarbamate. *Sci. Total Environ.* 727, 138701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138701>.
- Zhang, X., Mai, Y., Xian, X., Hu, L., Huang, J., Yuan, H., Lin, X., 2022. Adsorption and removal of phosphate from wastewater using lignin-based adsorbent modified with lanthanide: characterization, performance, and mechanisms. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61, 18069–18079. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c03208>.
- Zhang, F., Wang, C., Wang, X., Wang, J., Jiang, H., Xu, K., Bai, Y., Wang, P., 2023. Fabrication of raspberry-like starch-based polymer microspheres for W/O and O/W emulsions separation and purification. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11, 109260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.109260>.